

Modern Matrix Computations and Applied Mathematics, a Survey

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Abstract

This paper describes new matrix based algorithms for a recent cluster of extraordinary results in six or more distinct branches of mathematics. These results are inter-connected in a complicated multi-dimensional web of dependencies and implications.

Our earliest cluster paper deals with fractional ODEs and the Proportional Secting method that accelerates FDE terminal value problems by factors of around 8 to 12 and it speeds up many engineering applications.

The (unitary) block-decomposition method for all real or complex square matrices $A_{n,n}$ (and all matrix flows $A(t)_{n,n}$) now offers the tools for abandoned central Quantum Theory questions from the 1920s and much more.

This research cluster has been inspired by a fundamental Physics problem that now can be solved by our new threshold block-decomposition algorithm and Johnson's hermitean Field of Values $F(t)$ function, in conjunction with predictive Zhang Neural Networks and a new threshold based combinatorial 0-1 matrix algorithm from physical electron data.

In Quantum Theory terms, our solution makes the accurate assessment of our Chemical Element Tables finally possible after 100 + years of not knowing.

All computational methods in this cluster are conditionally stable, with easy bypass steps for their rare failed runs. They all give us highly accurate results such as in our adapted AZNN method for static matrices A that finds nonsingular static matrix symmetrizers with small condition numbers for the first time.

Our new algorithm also solves the block-diagonalisability question for many matrices with problematic eigenvalues as they are listed in Matlab's 'Gallery'.

The latter was not suspected, considered, or known before.

Our cluster results combine Zhang Neural Networks, the Block-Diagonalisation Algorithm and a 0-1 logic Combinatorial Matrix Method to allow real time applications in many areas such as in solving century old Quantum Theory problems that would and could not be approached by Albert Einstein, Von Neumann or Niels Bohr in the 1920s.

It helps with Musk satellite-X retrievals, with Fracking and Fractional ODE problems, in optimizing Chemical Reactors and more, all applications now running flawlessly in real 50 Hz sensor time. Our research introduces a new unitarily invariant Matrix Normal Form whose qualities have not been studied and that can be applied to many applications.

Keywords : math history, numerical analysis, fractional ODE, shooting methods, proportional sectioning, Linear algebra, block-decomposition, invariant subspace theory, Mittag-Leffler function, quantum physics, time-varying, matrix problem, conditionally stable algorithm, Johnson matrix flow, neural network, zeroing neural network, discretized ZNN algorithm, field of values, matrix flow, matrix normal form, time-varying numerical algorithm, predictive numerical method, matrix symmetrizer, threshold based matrix algorithm, 0-1 combinatorial matrix algorithm

AMS Classifications : 15A18, 15A21, 15A23, 15A60, 15B57, 33E12, 34A08, 65F15, 65F30, 65J10, 97B40, 97H60, 81Q10

Article Text at

[https://webhome.auburn.edu/~uhligfd/
MathSurvey2026.pdf](https://webhome.auburn.edu/~uhligfd/MathSurvey2026.pdf)

10.5281/zenodo.19198471

0 : A Prolog on Mathematics History

The sole purpose of this Math Survey paper is to describe my recent work that helped to solve a century old Quantum Physics problem of Einstein, Neumann, Bohr, and Wigner. This fundamental Quantum result had lain open and unsolved since the 1920s. My solution depends on half a dozen new extraordinary results in Applications and Computational Mathematics and it shortens their CPU run times by up to 85 %. A new class of Threshold based Matrix Algorithms helps us along here.

Mathematics has had a long history of helping humans to succeed in their environment and with our live-hood, for million of years. When our ancestors began to domesticate animals and we herded them for our benefit, we needed to master Math Counting and our Integers to make sure that all of our herd were safely hoarded up for the night.

As some young ones were born in the spring, we learned to add Positive Numbers, and to Subtract or reduce their numbers mathematically when we slaughtered some for our winter food.

What were these early Number Systems like in those days? Counting on our fingers? How?

Were they mathematically different for every tribe or global region? Are there, or were there many or even hundred-fold different origins of Mathematics on Earth?

The Cuneiform carvers of Babylon and Sumeria had no name and no symbol for 'Zero'. They just left zero positions blank and performed simple row reductions without even a Concept of Fractions. Their highly educated scribes could solve most Linear Equations in up to 4 variables, and they did so quite accurately. Fast forward to today, 2026.

What is the position of Mathematics in our world right now in 2026? Is Math still needed? Is Math obsolete now? Where to has it developed? What drives Mathematics on, in our current World of the Internet, of AI, and in our Engineering Knowhow and Prowess? How may Mathematics help us to prepare our Young to be productive and knowledgeable in their future?

Is Math still needed today? What Math is?

How should Math be taught today?

With most of us *continuing* with *our University Teaching* as done before by us and by our teachers, for decades and centuries.

Or do *modern times* require *new modern approaches*?

What do our young want, what in Math?

What kind of Math are they looking for?

What do our students need to learn in Mathematics so that our Societies can prosper and our Cultures and Lifestyles can continue to succeed and grow?

this paper deals with a Survey of Modern Mathematics as we know it today. How had I come to learn such a broad swath of Mathematics, over many decades in my Research and by my Teaching of Mathematics to the Young, that it bore such valuable fruit in new ways just now.

The cluster of my works in the early 2020s began with me reading about the early appearances of the concepts behind, and the actual term of "Matrix Fields of Values" in the Mathematical Literature and History of the early 1900s.

A look at the historic origin of the 'Field of Values' (FoV) concept for matrices will be the start of this Math Research Survey article.

Otto Toeplitz in Berlin and Felix Hausdorff in Kiel were the first mathematicians to conceive of and introduce the Field of Values term (known in German as 'Wertebereich') into our math literature. Toeplitz first approached this topic at the Berlin Academy in 1902, when a student there, and he coined the term "Wertbereich" (without the plural 'e') in 1902/1918 in front of the Berlin Academy in an invited talk for his Doctor degree.

The mathematical language at the time had no such 'Field of Values' like terms or words. In Toeplitz' mind these concepts slowly originated from theoretical matrix and convexity computational ideas as he wanted to plot the boundary curve of this 'mathematical item' concretely.

Another approach of this subject originated in our study of multi-centuries (or even millennia) of operator polynomials of Linear Functions in infinite dimensional normed vector spaces and in

what we now call Banach spaces. These historic studies eventually morphed into Functional Analysis in the mid 1900s.

A deep knowledge of these works was applied by Felix Hausdorff to n dimensional vector sets under Linear Transformations and this eventually lead to our understanding of the convexity of the Field of Values for all real or complex square matrices.

The Mathematics that surround the historic genesis of the matrix Field of Values from around 1901 to 1919 are very well explained at the start of Fejér's paper [14] and in Isabelle Bensimon and Kalin Kostadinov's introduction [2]. Henry Minkowski's convex body theorem and proof from around 1900 for $n = 2$ are equally important for understanding the roots of Matrix Fields of Values. The general results on Convexity were eventually applied to the images of n -vectors in \mathbb{R}^2 that are generated by the Field of Values construct to find interior and boundary FoV points in the 1970s by Charlie Johnson [25] and by others.

The Field of Values boundary points were previously (and only theoretically, of course) obtained from the extreme eigenvalue eigenvectors x of $A_{n,n}$ after 'evaluating' the Rayleigh quotient $x^* A^* A x / x^* x \in \mathbb{R}^2$, in the 2-D range plane – again only abstractly. A detailed look at the Field of Values boundary theory from Henri Minkowski's Convex Body theory is offered by Daniel Comeaux in [6]. The works of Constantin Carathéodory [4, 5], Leopold Fejér [13, 14] and Ernst Steinitz [37] influenced both Otto Toeplitz' and Felix Hausdorff's subsequent works [40, 42, 41, 43] and [21] on the erstwhile only 'theoretical' construction of Matrix Field of Values of the beginning 1900s.

All of these earlier works, in turn, lay the groundwork for Charlie Johnson's final practical computational method for drawing the Field of

Values boundary curve in [25], when effective and accurate matrix eigen-computations had become available in Matrix Numerical Analysis in the form of John G. F. Francis' QR algorithm [16, 17, 19] and the reliable backward stable LAPACK codes, in and after the mid 1970s.

For 300 years and many more, the relation between the coefficients of various short power series such as Taylor Series, Fourier Series or of algebraic polynomials were widely scrutinized for their function or mapping properties around the globe. Which early power series snippets thereof could or would likely create poles or blow-ups in the full power series and which power series would transfer compact sets of leading power series coefficients into compact sets in their range space, for example. Such questions on compactness, closedness and finally on convexity were all intertwined abstractly; since Descartes' or Cardano's times and possibly much earlier, beginning with or before Archimedes, and his predecessors in antiquity, – and pursued all around the globe and in all languages.

These early studies all involved concepts in Algebra and Geometry, Analysis and Topology, and Number Theory. New Words and Concepts were coined first and some were adopted later into our global Math Language.

Eventually, nascent Matrix Theory was involved here after Seki, Leibniz, Cauchy, Gauss, Sylvester, Weierstrass and many others, with their contributions from the 1600s through the 1800s and beyond. And the areas of Matrix Theory, Matrix Computations, and Matrix Applications have grown ever since and are still growing today. Such mathematical efforts had historically many Applications elsewhere, especially in the expanding Engineering work of the beginning Industrial Revolution in the mid 1700s and in the 1800s in Europe, and likewise in the second half of the last century for our Engineering needs and technical advances.

And so forth, today and tomorrow – for our ever growing human needs and desires, see [9, 10, 59, 71] for some modern Applied Math examples. One popular question early on was whether or which leading power series 'snippets' could or would create points in their range space \mathbb{R}^2 in which the line between any two image points would consist entirely of image points or whether there could be gaps in their the connecting line.

These questions were often dealt with at the Academies of the early 1800s. Math Journals had not been started yet, except for Crelle's.

There were, however, various hand written Academy Reports in Paris, Berlin, Göttingen, in Oxford and Cambridge, in Pisa, Pilsen and Vienna etc. But it is very hard today to find exact references of who did what and when then.

Historically, these developments lead mathematicians to the notions of the closedness of sets, then to compact sets and their preservation under continuous maps, and to the concept of convexity and the desire to preserve some mathematical properties under 'power series snippet mappings'. If the input domain lay in certain ways in its space, what was the smallest range in \mathbb{R}^2 that would contain all snippet images and so forth.

By 1900, one could begin to see some future developments of the yet undefined "Field of Values" 'object' and its properties and eventually of the Field of Values boundary curve as worthy of study and concern by itself.

The inventors of the Field of Values (FoV) term, Otto Toeplitz and Felix Hausdorff, built their work on many earlier generations which culminated in Henry Minkowski's "kleinste konvexe Bereiche" studies and his books, his papers and lectures, see [2] and [6]. technical advances.

Here we quote four papers by Otto Toeplitz [40, 41, 42, 43] from 1902 through 1918, the latter of which suddenly shows how Minkowski and Fejér's and others' work on 'power series snippet mappings' applies directly to the Matrix Field of Values question.

Otto Toeplitz had studied the FoV by developing and using mainly Matrix Theory language and concepts, see his doctoral thesis of 1901/1902 [40] which still looks very modern today.

Toeplitz eventually proved in 1918 [43] that the line segment between any two FoV points contains only FoV points and that the FoV points were always connected and filled the connecting set of points in the range space.

Felix Hausdorff approached the FoV problem differently, namely from his knowledge of the multi-dimensional or infinite dimensional domain extension of Minkowski et al's finite dimensional domain. Hausdorff started with vectors in \mathbb{R}^n or \mathbb{C}^n and n by n matrices. Then he used the field of value boundary point generating algorithm as his mapping between vectors in \mathbb{R}^n or \mathbb{C}^n and our 2-D plotting plane, see [21].

Thus we learned from both almost simultaneously in 1918/1919 that the Field of Values of every square matrix is convex, see [21] and [43].

And it took another hundred and six years to obtain the same result for matrix flows, see [56] and [57].

These historic algebraic and analytic, and topological and geometric results paved the way for our modern numerical Fields of Values studies and their use in applications from the 1960s through today. How to actually compute the Field of Values boundary curve numerically was introduced and studied by Charlie Johnson [24, 25] and others only after the invention of Electronic Computers and the development of reliable Mathematical Software from the 1940s into the 1970s. technical advances.

1 : An Introduction to a set of new Fundamental Math Results with some New Proof Outlines

These new Results from the early 2020s are all interconnected, some of these date back a hundred or more years. They all hinge on new branches and new parts of Matrix Theory and Matrix Computations. These were developed by the author, with help from many others, over many decades, along the way.

For general complex or real 1-parameter matrix flows $A(t)_{n,n}$ or for static matrices $A \in \mathbb{C}^{n,n}$, this paper considers ways to block-decompose matrix flows $A(t)_{n,n}$ or single matrices $A_{n,n}$ globally via one constant matrix similarity $C_{n,n}$ into a block-diagonal form with unitary diagonal blocks and zeros elsewhere.

Many of the new cluster results hinge on the new Block-Diagonalisation Algorithm (BDA), where

$$A(t) = C^{-1} \cdot \text{diag}(A_1(t), \dots, A_\ell(t)) \cdot C \quad (\text{X})$$

or

$$A = C^{-1} \cdot \text{diag}(A_1, \dots, A_\ell) \cdot C . \quad (\text{XX})$$

Here each diagonal block $A_k(t)$ or A_k is unitary, square, and their number ℓ exceeds 1 – if this is possible, and – if A or $A(t)$ are actually properly block-diagonalisable. The theory and ideas behind our new Class of Computational Matrix Algorithms are elementary, but difficult to implement. They use the modern concept of invariant subspaces (see Dave Watkins seminal work from the 1980s, for example) for Matlab's `eig` computed 'eigenvectors' of one flow matrix $A(t_a)$. Then they use a Threshold based Combinatorial Logic 0-1 Matrix Algorithm to find the coarsest simultaneous block structure of all other flow matrices $A(t_b)$ with $t_b \neq t_a$, if such a proper block-decomposition exists for the chosen matrix or matrix flow and the threshold.

Our Block-Decomposing Algorithm of [56] and [57] block-diagonalizes any given matrix flow $A(t)$ or any given static matrix A – as finely as possible, depending on the user’s choice of the threshold.

Specifically, our new BDA method works efficiently in around $O(n^{2.5})$ time for all square matrices $A_{n,n}$ and all square time-varying matrix flows $A(t)$, be they real or complex, normal, with Jordan structures or repeated eigenvalues, and be they differentiable, continuous, or discontinuous.

Our intended aim all along was to discover block-decomposable matrices and matrix flows as they might originate in real-time from time-varying sensor data. For block-diagonalisable n by n A or $A(t)$, the complexity of their numerical treatment decreases swiftly for $O(n^3)$ matrix processes when adopting ‘divide and conquer’ methods on each of their diagonal blocks separately, see the Appendices in [56].

Proof : *Block-Decomposition and Fast and Accurate Field of Values Boundary Computations of all Square Matrices*

The Block-Decomposition of matrix flows or single square matrices has never been resolved by algebraic means in 100 + years and it has possibly never even been tried, because there seemed to be no algebraic way or ideas to start from, – before the advent of computers and matrix based software such as Matlab, Matematica, Octave and so forth.

Instead, our new way of testing and establishing block-decomposability of a matrix $A_{n,n}$ or a matrix flow $A(t)_{n,n}$ hinges entirely on a Threshold Based Numerical Algorithm that decides the issue depending on the lay of the near zero entries and of the sizable ones in the associated hermitean Johnson matrix flow

$$\mathcal{F}(t) = \cos(t)H + \sin(t)K \quad (\text{XXX})$$

for $0 \leq t \leq 2\pi$ and $H = (A + A^*)/2$ and $K = (A - A^*)/2i$, the hermitean and skew hermitean parts of $A_{n,n}$ or $A(t)_{n,n}$.

[For simplicity of presentation, we assume that all matrices A and matrix flows $A(t)$ are real in this paper. Everything is similarly true for complex matrices.]

Our Block-Diagonalizing Algorithm (BDA) uses the Francis QR eigenvalue method to find the block-diagonal structure of one hermitean Johnson flow matrix $\mathcal{F}(t)$.

But the algorithm otherwise operates completely differently from Francis' hermitean QR and constructs

a new, previously unknown and totally different Matrix Normal Form.

Matrix normal forms generally try to represent a linear transform as simply as possible in an appropriate basis. Francis QR starts from a Hessenberg form for the given matrix A and then tries to upper triangularize A with its 'eigenvalues' appearing on the diagonal and small fill-in in the rest of the upper triangle – if possible.

(Complex eigen-pairs will become 2-dimensional diagonal blocks in Francis QR with a wild upper triangle elsewhere.)

Unfortunately, some complicated eigenstructures for A with repeated eigenvalues or with eigenvalues and principal values cannot be found reliably using Francis QR. Besides, Francis QR can only work on one matrix A at a time and it can not be used for matrix flows $A(t)$. But it is still our workhorse for eigen questions and comparisons today. The accelerating diagonal shifts of Francis QR finally render an upper diagonal matrix under a complicated matrix similarity with A 's 'eigenvalues' generally appearing on the 'diagonal'.

Our (unitary) Block-Diagonalization Algorithm instead creates a block diagonal normal form for all square matrices A and all matrix flows $A(t)$, real or complex. Here the sizes of the unitary square diagonal blocks always depend on a user chosen error Threshold.

Our new BDA algorithm computes a block-diagonal matrix structure $diag(A_1, \dots, A_\ell)$ or $diag(A_1(t), \dots, A_\ell(t))$ for any static square matrix A or any matrix flow $A(t)$, with a clear all zero upper right block matrix and a clear all zero lower left block matrix and unitary square blocks A_i or $A_i(t)$ along the main diagonal. It does so with one similarity $C^{-1} \dots C$ as was described in formulas (X) and (XX) earlier.

Many uses have been developed for the backward stable Francis QR algorithm over time, while the potential of our new conditionally stable Block-Diagonalisation Algorithm has not been studied, nor much developed yet. Some early applications such as solving the still open Quantum Physics problem from the 1920s or the nonsingular matrix symmetrizer problem will be explained in more detail later-on in this paper.

The (unitary) Block-Diagonalisation Algorithm might also show its worth in higher dimensional matrix problems such as for Tensor Flows, where it might become useful in photographic studies of digitized images and in image restoration, as well as in image authentication and forensic studies of image manipulations, see [59] e.g. . And possibly do so also in improving chemical and biological reactor optimizations, see [51] for examples.

One just cannot tell BDA's true potential; it is all too soon ...

Our Block-Diagonalisation Algorithm starts from two Johnson flow matrices $\mathcal{F}(t_1)$ and $\mathcal{F}(t_2)$ that are linearly independent. Then we form the 0-1 logic matrices $Flogic(t_1)$ and $Flogic(t_2)$ in Matlab's `spy` function and assemble the normalized eigen-

vectors of $\mathcal{F}(t_1)$ combinatorially in $V'(t_1)$ (' meaning: the hermitean transpose of V here) so that adjacent rows in $Flogic(t_1)$ have equal 0 and 1 patterned row blocks, if possible.

Next we reorder the rows of $Flogic(t_2)$ so that they have the same 0-1 pattern as $Flogic(t_1)$ (if possible) and thereafter we continue the block-diagonalization process with logic 0-1 matrices only. Then our logic 0-1 pattern matrix codes all use a simple logic combinatorial algorithm that establishes and refines a joint proper block-decomposition of both logic 0-1 spy pattern matrices of $V(t_1)$ and $V(t_2)$ cheaply, – if that is possible; see [55] through [58].

To prove the main unitary Diagonalability Theorem [56], we assume that for any matrix $A_{n,n}$ the hermitean Johnson flow $\mathcal{F}(t)$ contains two linearly independent matrices $\mathcal{F}(t_a) \neq \mathcal{F}(t_b)$ where $\mathcal{F}(t) = \cos(t)H + \sin(t)K$ for the hermitean and the skew parts $H = (A + A^*)/2$ and $K = (A - A^*)/(2i)$ of $A_{n,n}$, see formula (XXX) above.

Going down from the top block then leads to a joint block-diagonal structure for all $\mathcal{F}(t)$ with $t \in [0, 2\pi]$. Since $\mathcal{F}(0) = H$ and $\mathcal{F}(\pi/2) = K$, the matrix A or the flow $A(t)$ themselves have the same block structure as the unitary matrices $V(t_1)$ and $V(t_2)$ do, and our block-diagonalisation of A or $A(t)$ is complete.

What is going on here? To begin this section, we had stipulated that for simplicity we were only going to deal with real matrices A and real matrix flows $A(t)$ here, see Equation (XXX) above.

Why would we talk of 'hermitean matrices' here where symmetric ones would suffice? And : How do we best designate the transpose of real matrices or matrix flows, by A^T , A' , or $A^t(t)$ in Matlab or other Software?

These notational quandaries depend on the context. And I will not repeat every block-diagonalisation result or statement here with referring to both cases of over \mathbb{R} or over \mathbb{C} , and both static or flowing matrices. These statements are all true.

This algorithm depends, however, on the magnitude relations between the non-zero entries and the near zero entries in $\mathcal{F}(t_i)$ for $i = 1, 2$ and a Threshold.

If the chosen threshold is too small, there might be no discernible block structure at all and if it is too large, then the block diagonal structure might only show the non-zero block entries on the diagonal of an ill 'computed' block-diagonal matrix.

To distinguish between computed entries as being 'zero' or definitely 'nonzero' is an uncharted question. For the moment, we have set the 'zero' threshold heuristically to

$$\|A\|_{fro} \cdot 10^{-13} \approx \|A\|_{fro} \cdot eps$$

for the Frobenius 2-norm when working with matrices A in double precision and the machine constant $eps \approx 2.2 \cdot 10^{-16}$ of Matlab.

We must repeat : Our constructive numerical proof hinges on an algorithm that is able to distinguish between the near zero entries and the definitely non-zero entries of a matrix or matrix flow accurately and reliably. We know of no way to prove the block-diagonalization theorem algebraically. And our numerical proof depends on an appropriate 'near zero' threshold.

An algebraic proof of our result was never attempted. We dare to claim that an algorithmic proof was impossible before the advent of computers and a deeper understanding of matrix flows such as the hermitean Johnson flow $\mathcal{F}(t)$ and the predictive qualities and high accuracy of Zhang Neural Networks, as brought to light recently in ZNN [70], [62] and AZNN [60].

The ability to construct the field of values $\mathcal{F}(A)$ boundary curve of some unitarily decomposable matrices quickly and accurately via shooting methods led to recent further studies of matrix eigencurve behavior by many authors who tried to locate their crossings (or hyperbolic avoidances thereof) that had first appeared in original Quantum Physics studies by von Neumann and Paul Wigner [33, p. 469], in Copenhagen, in Berlin, and in Göttingen; in the 1920s, see the drawing on p. 21.

At the time, Albert Einstein shunned this fundamental Quantum Theory problem and rather worked on Relativity. Niels Bohr's group wanted to understand eigencurve crossings and their relation to the matrix block-decomposability of matrices, but neither Albert, nor Niels, or their research groups succeeded then.

Eigencurve crossing studies for the still un-resolved block-diagonalisation problem that affects Quantum Theory so enormously would begin anew with Charlie Johnson's work [24, 25] on the field of values in the 1970s and pick up again in the 1990s in Luca Dieci et al.'s papers [7, 8] and in many other papers of Luca's research group, and by others, and also in Sébastien Loisel and Peter Maxwell's paper [28], as well as in some of my eigencurve papers such as [53], [55], [56], and [63].

This development continued until around 2020, when several small partial results (maybe 12 or 15 %) of the block-decomposition problem had been solved. But no complete classification had been found and the century old problems with eigencurve crossings were still open in 2023 until [56] appeared in print.

My final classification of block-decompositions [56] for both, general matrix flows and static matrices, was ultimately inspired by Yunong Zhang's parameter-varying Neural Networks (ZNN) that date back to Yunong's doctoral thesis [69] of 2001.

These recent results are all inter-woven and they all have contributed to each other's solutions and to the author's understanding of this cluster's six or seven inter-connected new fundamental computational results and to finding their proofs. Each of the new results has advanced its area tremendously, where no new math methods or algorithms had been found for decades or longer, by dedicated researchers that tried to use our canon of standardly known analytical tools.

The mathematical process that obtained these results was never predictable – until everything fell into place in 2022/24, when everything was mathematically sound, and had been proved and tested. My papers were quickly accepted and printed with global free open access (OA) without my suggesting this, by their respective Editors-in-Chief.

Note that my conditionally stable Matrix Computational Algorithms in this research cluster do not solve any nearby problem accurately – as *backward stable* methods are designed to do.

Instead, the new methods deliver highly accurate results at high speed and they do not suffer from the high inaccuracies in the traditional 'backward stable' fashion that we are accustomed to. Conditionally stable algorithms were often shunned by the numerical analysis community, see the fate of [18] from 2008 for example. The reports on this paper by the editor and four referees dealt with the questionable usefulness and quality of our theoretical and numerical matrix methods.

More specifically, the reports asserted that we had not used 'stable methods', by which they meant "backward stable methods", but instead, we had used Cleve Moler's Matlab m-files in place of John Francis' 'stable' QR eigenvalue algorithm and the fully compiled 'backward stable' LAPACK codes.

(ugh ... !)

Our new methods can all encounter rare breakdowns that are easily bypassed, and when bypassed, they give us near exact results in the end, see [60], e. g. .

Adapted ZNN [60] for example has solved the open and previously unsolvable matrix symmetrizer problem in [11] where we had been unable to find invertible matrix symmetrizers by using John Francis' QR [16, 17], Gene Golub and Velvel Kahan's SVD [20], several optimization algorithms, and so forth, but had failed to find nonsingular symmetric matrix factorizations $\hat{S} \cdot A = T$, even for real matrices A , with a symmetric matrix $T = T'$ and a nonsingular symmetric \hat{S} , see [39].

Our all-out efforts in [11] were also challenged by matrices with repeated eigenvalues or difficult Jordan structures from Matlab's 'Gallery'. The 'standard methods' of [11] failed to compute invertible symmetrizers for many of those gallery matrices.

Next we highlight the Theorems and Matrix Algorithms that were instrumental in this research cluster.

We start with

(a) ZNN

Zhang Neural Networks (ZNN) for matrix problems were invented two decades ago, see [69]. Their workings are explained in detail for discretized matrix problems in [62]. Today they are used extensively in robot control and other modern engineering problems that need real-time, predictive and accurate solutions.

My ZNN paper [62] explains their workings in 7 steps for many standard single parameter matrix processes.

Discretized ZNN starts from an error equation $e(t)$.

$$(1) \quad e(t) = \begin{array}{l} \text{exact solution} \\ \text{- computed solution} \\ \text{at time } t. \end{array}$$

Exponentially fast Convergence of ZNN is assured by stipulating that the error function $e(t)$ decreases exponentially in the discretized 'time variable t ' t_k .

$$(2) \quad \dot{e}(t) = -\alpha \cdot e(t) \quad \text{for } \alpha > 0.$$

Then users have to (3) solve this ODE algebraically for $\dot{e}(t_k)$, which may be impossible. If impossible, the error function (1) has to be expressed differently or a more involved problem set-up may be needed, see [62] for such occurrences.

Zhang Neural Networks rely on convergent parametrized 1-step ahead finite

$$(4) \quad \text{difference formulas.}$$

In [54] we have constructed several convergent look-ahead formulas using the forward Taylor expansion of $e(t)$. See [66] for another method to develop convergent 1-step ahead finite difference formulas with rational coefficients.

After (5) choosing one predictive convergent formula from the list in [54] or [66] according to the desired error order, and

(6) equating the expressions for $\dot{e}(t_{k+1})$ in (3) and (5), simply solve the resulting derivative free equation for the future solution $x(t_{k+1})$ at time t_{k+1} .

And in (7) we iterate the process.

Yunong Zhang's Neural Networks are central to our recent research. They are uniquely capable to guarantee fast convergence due to the exponential error decay stipulation in (2) and they are predictive since they find $x(t_{k+2})$ from the evaluations of the Taylor expansions for $e(t_{k+1})$ in (3) and $e(t_k)$ in (5). This process here uses only two start-up values. ZNN generally uses between 3 and 6 start-up data points. For further details see [62].

Historically, the Quantum Physicists of the 1920s recognized that eigencurve crossings were involved with possible groupings of chemical elements into

connected or disconnected groups from their electron data, see the picture on p. 21 below. The path following ODE method of Loisel and Maxwell [28] recently solved a small portion of the eigen-curve problem and this inspired me to use ZNN in conjunction with Johnson's field of values boundary plotting method [25]. This is the most accurate and cheapest way today to solve Toeplitz and Hausdorff's Field of Values result today numerically, see [56, Applications].

(b) Adapted ZNN

The Adapted ZNN method (AZNN) of [60] studies the effects of varying the decay constant α in the error function ODE (2) over time. AZNN changes the ZNN finite difference formula used in different stages of the iterations, as well as adapting the unstable simple Euler iteration to achieve a quicker error decay at start-up — these approaches are counter-intuitive, but they work very well.

With an appropriately adapted AZNN method, see [60], we were able to compute nonsingular matrix symmetrizers $S = S^T$ with $S \cdot A = T$ and $A = S^{-1} \cdot T$ for $T = T^T$ for all square matrices A with symmetrizing errors generally less than Matlab's `eps` and with very small condition numbers for stable invertibility of the left side symmetric factor S to achieve $A = S^{-1} \cdot T$. This was generally impossible before with standard matrix methods; see [11, Section 4].

(c) Plotting the Boundary Curve of the Field of Values

The field of values of a matrix (FOV) has been studied by Toeplitz [43] since the early 1900s and also by Hausdorf [21] in 1918/1919 as a 'theoretical' means to estimate the eigenvalues of matrices.

In 1978, Johnson [25] proposed a 'practical way' to plot the FOV boundary of matrices numerically, using the hermitean matrix flow :

$$\mathcal{F}(t) = \cos(t)H + \sin(t)K \quad (= (\mathcal{F}(t))^*)$$

for the hermitean part $H = (A + A^*)/2 = H^*$ and the skew hermitean part $K = (A - A^*)/(2i) = K^*$ of $A_{n,n}$ for $t \in [0, 2\pi]$, and evaluating both eigenvectors x for the two real extreme eigenvalues of the hermitean matrices $\mathcal{F}(t)$ and plotting them in the rotated plane via the quadratic form x^*Ax/x^*x ; for details see [25].

This idea was adapted by Sébastien Loisel and Peter Maxwell in [28] into a path following ODE for the slope of $\mathcal{F}(t)$ that bested Johnson's algorithm [25] in run time and accuracy. And a ZNN based path following was finally adopted to the FoV problem for even better results in [60]. Today ZNN path following is the best method known for an accurate depiction of the matrix FoV boundary curve.

ZNN is designed for general square matrices or matrix flows, be they real or complex. For additional speed-up ZNN should be combined with the block-diagonalizing result of [56], see subsections (d) and (e) below.

(d) Eigencurves

My earlier research [50, 52, 55] on eigencurve behavior lead directly to this cluster's centerpiece in part (e), i.e., the numerical discovery of the finest block-diagonal structure for general square matrices $A_{n,n}$ or matrix flows $A_{n,n}(t)$ by one fixed similarity $C^{-1} A \dots C$ in [56].

Sébastien Loisel and Peter Maxwell [28] had tested their fast ODE path following FOV method in 2018 on block-diagonal matrices and noted that eigencurve crossings for the maximal eigenvalue created unsolvable havoc for block-diagonal matrix flows with overlapping block spectra. Likewise, Luca

Dieci and multiple co-authors, see [7, 8] for example, had worked on the eigencurve crossing problem for 20 years and could not succeed to plot FOVs of general unitarily block-diagonalisable matrices. Their eigencurve crossings research and methods were seemingly abandoned around 2020 with no way for algebraic proofs or computational algorithms.

This quest had been started in Quantum Physics about a century ago by von Neumann, Friedrich Herman Hund and Eugene Paul Wigner, see [33], [23] and their graphical depiction of eigencurve crossings below.

I had become interested in the eigencurve crossing problem in [55, 56] and this has led me to discover a solution to the century old block-diagonalization problem for matrices in [56] – after I had understood Johnson’s $\mathcal{F}(t)$ function and ZNN iterations more deeply.

Drawing of 'eigencurve crossings' and their hyperbolic avoidance from [33, p. 469] and [23].

Curve β_1 crosses E_2 and E_1 and avoids β_2 .

Curve β_2 crosses only E_1 and avoids all other curves in a hyperbolic way.

Many fundamental Linear Algebra insights from the classical 19th century and from the modern computational a from the 1930s on were equally important for the inter-twining results of this research cluster presentation.

I have described the history of our area in mathematics in detail to keep us aware of the importance and value of all of it that was discovered eons ago and recently.

We need to be conscious of mathematics' history and learn to cherish and use all of it today.

(e) Faster Computational Methods for Unitarily Decomposable Matrices

Of special interest here are square matrices with involved Jordan structures and with any (previously unknown) block-diagonalizability problems. To our surprise, about one quarter of the matrices in Matlab's 'Gallery' with difficult eigen-structures are block diagonalizable. This had not been known or even thought about before, because there had been no appropriate tools for a hundred and more years to (unitarily) block-diagonalize.

Checking for block-diagonalizability before working on many matrices of the same kind will shorten computational run times greatly, as shown extensively in the AZNN paper [60, Sections 2, 3.1 and 3.2, Figures 1 through 14 and Tables 1 and 2].

Structured sparse matrices such as Toeplitz, Hankel, Circulant and other striped matrices from finite difference methods for boundary value problems come to mind here as well. Figure 6 in [60] explains the high benefits of even relatively large maximal block sizes for speeding up unitarily blockdiagonalisable matrix computations.

The long term behavior of ZNN methods for time-varying real matrix square roots for example, shows an ever downward decreasing exponentially decaying error function, see [60, Figure 1].

With properly chosen AZNN parameters, after around 16 minutes, the error size of time-varying matrix square roots generally decrease smoothly into the 10^{-18} or lower error range.

Eventually small computational rounding errors of AZNN led to matrix square roots with negative 'entries' and the computed matrix iterates would then bifurcate, with some test matrix entries becoming

complex conjugate pairs. These would stay non-real until the matrix square root entries became all real again. Then the complex bifurcation would end and all would stay real for a while in the sub-sub 10^{-18} range, with a continually decreasing error function. See [60].

There are several open questions here on the behavior of time-varying discretized ZNN methods. How can one connect the error threshold of machine constant magnitude with incoming ZNN data and uniformly restart the ZNN process when needed. Recall that well conditioned symmetrizers of static matrices were computed by AZNN with errors well below 10^{-18} .

Our evidence, however, suggests that it is detrimental to run time-varying ZNN or AZNN for durations exceeding 16 or 18 minutes in double precision computations and therefore into the exponential decay problem zone. Such as for matrix square roots after some 40,000 iteration steps (and more than 2 hours of simulated runtime) when using time-varying ZNN at the 50Hz standard clock rate $\tau = 0.02$ sec here for example, see [60, Figure 1].

We generally advise to restart the process well before the 'errors' have become smaller than the floating point machine constant $\epsilon \sim 10^{-16}$ in Matlab's double precision arithmetic that carries 16 digits.

(f) The Proportional Secting Method for Fractional Differential equations

This section seems peripheral mathematically to our present multi-faced mathematical research cluster, but its results and methods are central to much of Mathematics, once we appreciate its Applications in Modern Engineering. Applications and Modern Engineering Questions are central to all of my recent and older work and my research methods will soon become clear.

The paper [10] by Kai Diethelm and Frank Uhlig originated after a Zoom talk by Kai on Fractional Differential Equations (FDEs) on the Irish Numerical Analysis Forum (INA) Zoom Talks in 2021. Frank contacted Kai about the selection of shooting points to start the FDE iterations and otherwise he suggested to continue with the numerical methods that were then commonly used in this area.

Fractional derivatives occur naturally in FDE systems when non-local effects are present in the physical model. Here ‘non-local’ may refer to both time or space variables. This typically happens in mathematical models if the properties of a material exhibit memory dependent behavior changes such as with viscoelastic materials, in fracking simulations, and so forth. Only a few efficient methods are generally used to solve initial value problems for FDEs. These are mostly concerned with optimizing their step sizes.

In practical terms, this section (**f**) rounds out our earlier cut-off polynomial or power series approach to convexity, compactness and the like in the development of the early 1900s and in the early ‘theoretic’ FOV problem for matrices then.

The fractional differential problems and algorithms go back to Goesta Magnus Mittag-Leffler [30, 31, 32] in the mid 1900s as well. These were recently used, expanded upon and described by Ronald L. Bagey, by Michelle Caputo, by YangQuan Chen, by Neville Ford, by Allen D. Freed, by Roberto Garrappa, by Rudolf Gorenflo, by Christian Lubich, by Mark M. Maerschaert, by Francesco Mainardi, by Igor Podlubny, by Arnold Ross, by Peter J. Torvik, by Hoang The Tuan, and by Kai Diethelm and myself, and by their and our students and collaborators, and by many many others around the globe.

For details, refer to the text and the References in [10], then look at the comparison images in [59] on

p. 12, at the runtime data on p. 15 and 19, and at the proofs in two appendices, p. 21 - 31 of [59].

The new matrix based method [59], applied for fractional ODEs, uses only simple problem specific Matrix Arithmetic and does not enter into Tensor methods for image restoration or authentication. Therefore it works around 3 times faster than today's standard methods for image analysis and the new shooting method of Diethelm and Uhlig [10] now allows us to cut out around 85 % of the iterations in FDE computations.

The classical ODE solvers are the workhorse computational building blocks that take up most of the FDE CPU runtimes. They are generally combined with the classical bisection method which can only halve the feasible shooting point intervals in each step.

Note that the first search interval can be astronomically large and complicated as the classical estimation techniques for the starting interval points bounds often require us to evaluate Mittag-Leffler Functions (MLFs) with large positive arguments. When containment intervals with upper bounds of around 10^7 units occur on one side of the 'correct shooting start', and with just 2 units on the other side, the classical bisection methods will iterate dozens of times as they only halve the search interval's size, going slowly, step by step.

The book by Keith Oldham and Jerome Spanier [34] is a good starting point for learning about Fractional Difference ODEs, as is the survey article on Matrix MLfs and Numerical Computations thereof by Marina Popolizio [35].

We have started in Section 1 with studying the genesis of the Field of Values and exploring its roots in antiquity and now end this paper with some of the most technical Modern Matrix Computations of 'snippet' matrix behavior in Applied Math and cutting edge Engineering Applications.

Two 'bookends' of sorts for this survey paper and a good way to conclude it.

The result in [10] is an extraordinary advance. The Proportional Secting Method (PSM) uses around 1/10th of the bisection method iterations. PSM gets done in around 1/10th of the standard shooting methods' CPU time. And when joined by predictive ZNN, our PSM algorithm can solve FDEs in 50 Hz real sensor time.

PSM can simplify Elon Musk's way of returning Space X modules vertically to earth, it can be applied in Environmental studies of Fracking groundwater contaminations, see [71] or seminal papers on the far reaching effects on our aquifers from Fracking, by AJ Meir and others at Auburn University, the NSF, and SMU, and the list goes on and on.

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Today Fractional ODEs appear in many different Engineering Problems and serve in multiple Applications. Their solution methods are indispensable as a computational backbone of our Modern Life, of Engineering, and our Industry.

PSM is simple to implement. It always uses the latest two starting points to determine the next shooting start, except for the first iteration that is (at this moment) still determined via MLF [30, 31, 32] estimates. Efforts to dismiss all MLF type evaluations completely in our accelerated computational FDE solver [10] are under way.

The proportional secting iterates are computed without any logical "if" loops or any interval containment requirements. Thus PSM is generally much faster in reducing any MLF based or other initial shooting interval.

At the time of our investigations in [10], some of the FDE shooters were exploring the effects of using low accuracy solution at the beginning of the FDE integration process and other such speed-up ideas. These improvements would sometimes reduce their relatively large total iterations counts by 1 or 2 steps or increase them similarly, but not by near 90 % as PSM in [10] does.

Reasons for this behavior of the 'classical' bisection based FDE solvers were debated and never found. And the future direction for developing new FDE solvers was stuck in limbo – until [10] appeared; which ended these efforts gracefully.

My bad ... , creating math unemployment

...

This ends my math cluster presentations, with selections from an extraordinarily rich and fundamentally new part of Mathematics.

This paper has been designed with two separate purposes in mind :

The first, the Mathematics Survey part, has detailed new fundamental Research in Mathematics.

Now we need to think about how to propagate our current math advances into our educational methods for teaching mathematics.

My main question and concern here is :

How can we do this globally, and in fact for our own survival on Earth?

By advancing Mathematics and Math Applications or by also, or even foremost, advancing our Educational Methods and Modernizing our Subject Lists.

A separate, second paper [65] will address our elementary Linear Algebra teachings and deal with the globe-wide problem of "teaching for the test" in our mostly 'top-down' lecturing and in our unfortunate efforts to teach Modern Mathematics to our young.

These recent teaching developments have lead to our Most Urgent Problem in all of Mathematics today.

Solving this problem will involve Linear Algebra and Matrices necessarily.

Because Matrices are at the very basis of all of our Communications and Computations around the Globe and in Space.

Matrices and Matrix Computations uniquely support our Internet based Lives, our Search Engines and AI, our Banking and E-mailings, our podcasting and so forth.

Everything is ultimately computed via Matrix Algebra and Matrix Algorithms today on our Digital or Quantum Computers and Servers.

But unfortunately we are generally not conveying Linear Algebra well and most of us do not even try to use modern Interactive Teaching Methods – even after Covid and its changes in our consciousness, worldwide.

Nor are we introducing Modern Matrix Theory or Matrix Computational Methods adequately to our Young.

To our beginning students, – not at all to our Young

Removing these discrepancies is our most urgent

task to resolve in Mathematics

Today

Healing these discrepancies is more important for our own survival on Earth and in Space than all our recent engineering and mathematical advances, even those that now go beyond Albert Einstein's and Niels Bohr's understandings of the 1920s.

This task, pressing us all, is more urgent than finding any modern solutions of even century old unsolved fundamental Math problems, or in Physics, in Chemistry, in Quantum Theory, in Engineering, in Fracking research, in FDEs, in Biology, and in Matrix Flows and Neural Networks, for example, and in abstract Mathematics today, and on and on, so I think.

Our elementary Math Teachings Problems today require and deserve more coordinated efforts than Mathematicians are willing to give.

Are there any problems in our early College Linear Algebra Teaching or Teachings?

In Subjects taught or ... , where do our Problems lie – if any ?

In Linear Algebra and Matrix Theory, what is wrong with it ?

Teaching and/or Research wise ?

What needs to be done immediately ?

Clearly, we must modernize our early College Syllabi

in Linear Algebra and enliven this area of Mathematics.

Specifically, in this area that helps us so extraordinarily well in our daily Cell-phone and Internet based lives, in AI and in our Engineering advances today.

How do we, how do You mostly teach beginners' Linear Algebra classes today ?

Which Subjects do *we*, do *you*, and *I* teach ?

Using modern Matrix Theory based ideas *or* from a classical and historical algebraic standpoint ?

Top-down taught *or* taught Interactively ?

These are our most urgent questions today,

in All of Mathematics

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Our Outer World with Trillions of Stars

What is their Mathematics, Trillion-fold

Imagine **BOLD**, and do so boldly Think and
succeed

It can be done

Conclusions

My conclusions are drawn from my decades of work with various fundamental mathematical problems and the serendipity to continue effectively in my Mathematics Research, without a clear, predefined goal or a final plan in mind, but always progressing with silent hope and confidence on my path through Mathematics and its Applications.

Eventually I developed a new computational method that computes orthogonal bases for invariant subspaces of general square matrices or matrix flows.

Once that had been achieved and tested, this result - and together with many other results - helped me to solve fundamental Quantum Physics, Quantum Chemistry and other long abandoned discussions thereabout as well. These questions had been considered by Albert Einstein, Von Neumann and Niels Bohr in the 1920s. And they had never found a solution before.

This result from 2024 has had many contributors over many years from around the globe, in many separate fields of Mathematics, its Applications, and in Math Education.

These efforts finally jelled to let me resolve Einstein's, Neumann's and Bohr's open Quantum problems of the 1920s, much to my surprise.

Methods

The actual proof of the Unitary Matrix Block-Decomposition algorithm (BDA) has been at the heart of many new 'methods'. Nobody could have predicted this fundamental Theorem. To obtain it I needed deep and broad understandings of Matrix Flows, of Johnson's Field of Values flow $\mathcal{F}(t)$, and of the Inner Workings of Zhang Neural Networks, all gained in the 2020s.

The final proof of BDA is a convoluted mixture of these and other methods, some from antiquity, in a multi-dimensional implications diagram of interdependencies that I cannot dis-entangle in two or three dimensions.

I do not know my 'Math working methods' very well, nor do I understand them fully – but finally I have succeeded here, where many others have failed, even quite recently, – in successfully taking the Einstein, Neumann and Bohr problem off the un-solved problems list.

Learning by myself and for myself on how to teach at Cologne University in 1965, and thereby learning in turn how to live with educational and mathematical uncertainties throughout all my life and in my work, — and succeeding unexpectedly and often, that has been my path and method of work ... and of play with Mathematics.

For the last 55 years, a Spiritual Force was there with me at every step of learning and it pushed me forward gently and slowly. It, she, or it opened vistas for me and let me see and develop new structures in Research Mathematics and in Mathematics Education over the last half century. I am grateful for that.

This survey is available at

<https://webhome.auburn.edu/~uhligfd/MathSurvey2026.pdf>

and at Zenodo **10.5281/zenodo.19198471**, both free for everyone.

compiled at 16:53, Sunday 28th June, 2026